

Supplementary Information

This document presents supplementary figures showing bias in the 1-in-10 year daily maximum temperature.

Calibration task

Figure S1: Bias in the 1-in-10 year daily maximum temperature (relative to the AGCD dataset) for the calibration assessment task. Results are shown for the ERA5 GCM (panel a), the BARPA-R RCM forced by that GCM (panel c), and various bias correction methods applied to those GCM (panel b) and RCM (panels d-g) data. (MAE = mean absolute error.)

Figure S2: Bias in the 1-in-10 year daily maximum temperature (relative to the AGCD dataset) for the calibration assessment task. Results are shown for the ERA5 GCM (panel a), the CCAM-v2203-SN RCM forced by that GCM (panel c), and various bias correction methods applied to those GCM (panel b) and RCM (panels d-g) data. (MAE = mean absolute error.)

Figure S3: Bias in the 1-in-10 year daily maximum temperature (relative to the AGCD dataset) for the calibration assessment task. Results are shown for the ERA5 GCM (panel a), the CCAM-v2105 RCM forced by that GCM (panel c), and various bias correction methods applied to those GCM (panel b) and RCM (panels d-g) data. (MAE = mean absolute error.)

Figure S4: Bias in the 1-in-10 year daily maximum temperature (relative to the AGCD dataset) for the calibration assessment task. Results are shown for the ACCESS-ESM1-5 GCM (panel a), the BARPA-R RCM forced by that GCM (panel c), and various bias correction methods applied to those GCM (panel b) and RCM (panels d-g) data. (MAE = mean absolute error.)

Figure S5: Bias in the 1-in-10 year daily maximum temperature (relative to the AGCD dataset) for the calibration assessment task. Results are shown for the ACCESS-ESM1-5 GCM (panel a), the CCAM-v2203-SN RCM forced by that GCM (panel c), and various bias correction methods applied to those GCM (panel b) and RCM (panels d-g) data. (MAE = mean absolute error.)

Figure S6: Bias in the 1-in-10 year daily maximum temperature (relative to the AGCD dataset) for the calibration assessment task. Results are shown for the ACCESS-ESM1-5 GCM (panel a), the CCAM-v2105 RCM forced by that GCM (panel c), and various bias correction methods applied to those GCM (panel b) and RCM (panels d-g) data. (MAE = mean absolute error.)

Figure S7: Bias in the 1-in-10 year daily maximum temperature (relative to the AGCD dataset) for the calibration assessment task. Results are shown for the EC-Earth3 GCM (panel a), the BARPA-R RCM forced by that GCM (panel c), and various bias correction methods applied to those GCM (panel b) and RCM (panels d-g) data. (MAE = mean absolute error.)

Figure S8: Bias in the 1-in-10 year daily maximum temperature (relative to the AGCD dataset) for the calibration assessment task. Results are shown for the EC-Earth3 GCM (panel a), the CCAM-v2203-SN RCM forced by that GCM (panel c), and various bias correction methods applied to those GCM (panel b) and RCM (panels d-g) data. (MAE = mean absolute error.)

Figure S9: Bias in the 1-in-10 year daily maximum temperature (relative to the AGCD dataset) for the calibration assessment task. Results are shown for the BARPA-R RCM forced by the CESM2 GCM (panel a) and various bias correction methods applied to those RCM data (panels b-e) data. Unlike the other GCMs, no raw CESM2 data were available. (MAE = mean absolute error.)

Figure S10: Bias in the 1-in-10 year daily maximum temperature (relative to the AGCD dataset) for the calibration assessment task. Results are shown for the CCAM-v2203-SN RCM forced by the CESM2 GCM (panel a) and various bias correction methods applied to those RCM data (panels b-e) data. Unlike the other GCMs, no raw CESM2 data were available. (MAE = mean absolute error.)

Cross validation task

Figure S11: Bias in the 1-in-10 year daily maximum temperature (relative to the AGCD dataset) for the cross validation assessment task. Results are shown for the ERA5 GCM (panel a), the BARPA-R RCM forced by that GCM (panel d), and various bias correction methods applied to those GCM (panels b and c) and RCM (panels e, f, g, i and j) data. A reference case where the AGCD training data (1960-1989) was simply duplicated for the assessment period (1990-2019) is also shown (panel h). (MAE = mean absolute error.)

Figure S12: Bias in the 1-in-10 year daily maximum temperature (relative to the AGCD dataset) for the cross validation assessment task. Results are shown for the ERA5 GCM (panel a), the CCAM-v2203-SN RCM forced by that GCM (panel d), and various bias correction methods applied to those GCM (panels b and c) and RCM (panels e, f, g, i and j) data. A reference case where the AGCD training data (1960-1989) was simply duplicated for the assessment period (1990-2019) is also shown (panel h). (MAE = mean absolute error.)

Figure S13: Bias in the 1-in-10 year daily maximum temperature (relative to the AGCD dataset) for the cross validation assessment task. Results are shown for the ERA5 GCM (panel a), the CCAM-v2105 RCM forced by that GCM (panel d), and various bias correction methods applied to those GCM (panels b and c) and RCM (panels e, f, g, i and j) data. A reference case where the AGCD training data (1960-1989) was simply duplicated for the assessment period (1990-2019) is also shown (panel h). (MAE = mean absolute error.)

Figure S14: Bias in the 1-in-10 year daily maximum temperature (relative to the AGCD dataset) for the cross validation assessment task. Results are shown for the ACCESS-ESM1-5 GCM (panel a), the BARPA-R RCM forced by that GCM (panel d), and various bias correction methods applied to those GCM (panels b and c) and RCM (panels e, f, g, i and j) data. A reference case where the AGCD training data (1960-1989) was simply duplicated for the assessment period (1990-2019) is also shown (panel h). (MAE = mean absolute error.)

Figure S15: Bias in the 1-in-10 year daily maximum temperature (relative to the AGCD dataset) for the cross validation assessment task. Results are shown for the ACCESS-ESM1-5 GCM (panel a), the CCAM-v2203-SN RCM forced by that GCM (panel d), and various bias correction methods applied to those GCM (panels b and c) and RCM (panels e, f, g, i and j) data. A reference case where the AGCD training data (1960-1989) was simply duplicated for the assessment period (1990-2019) is also shown (panel h). (MAE = mean absolute error.)

Figure S16: Bias in the 1-in-10 year daily maximum temperature (relative to the AGCD dataset) for the cross validation assessment task. Results are shown for the ACCESS-ESM1-5 GCM (panel a), the CCAM-v2105 RCM forced by that GCM (panel d), and various bias correction methods applied to those GCM (panels b and c) and RCM (panels e, f, g, i and j) data. A reference case where the AGCD training data (1960-1989) was simply duplicated for the assessment period (1990-2019) is also shown (panel h). (MAE = mean absolute error.)

Figure S17: Bias in the 1-in-10 year daily maximum temperature (relative to the AGCD dataset) for the cross validation assessment task. Results are shown for the EC-Earth3 GCM (panel a), the BARPA-R RCM forced by that GCM (panel d), and various bias correction methods applied to those GCM (panels b and c) and RCM (panels e, f, g, i and j) data. A reference case where the AGCD training data (1960-1989) was simply duplicated for the assessment period (1990-2019) is also shown (panel h). (MAE = mean absolute error.)

Figure S18: Bias in the 1-in-10 year daily maximum temperature (relative to the AGCD dataset) for the cross validation assessment task. Results are shown for the EC-Earth3 GCM (panel a), the CCAM-v2203-SN RCM forced by that GCM (panel d), and various bias correction methods applied to those GCM (panels b and c) and RCM (panels e, f, g, i and j) data. A reference case where the AGCD training data (1960-1989) was simply duplicated for the assessment period (1990-2019) is also shown (panel h). (MAE = mean absolute error.)

Figure S19: Bias in the 1-in-10 year daily maximum temperature (relative to the AGCD dataset) for the cross validation assessment task. Results are shown for the BARPA-R RCM forced by the CESM2 GCM (panel a) and various bias correction methods applied to those RCM data (panels b, c, d, f and g). A reference case where the AGCD training data (1960-1989) was simply duplicated for the assessment period (1990-2019) is also shown (panel e). Unlike the other GCMs, no raw CESM2 data were available. (MAE = mean absolute error.)

Figure S20: Bias in the 1-in-10 year daily maximum temperature (relative to the AGCD dataset) for the cross validation assessment task. Results are shown for the CCAM-v2203-SN RCM forced by the CESM2 GCM (panel a) and various bias correction methods applied to those RCM data (panels b, c, d, f and g). A reference case where the AGCD training data (1960-1989) was simply duplicated for the assessment period (1990-2019) is also shown (panel e). Unlike the other GCMs, no raw CESM2 data were available. (MAE = mean absolute error.)